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Black Sea Eutrophication Comparative Analysis of Intensity between Coastal and Offshore Waters

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Abstract: Eutrophication, driven by excessive nutrient enrichment from sources like agricultural runoff, industrial discharge, and urbanisation, has severely impacted the Black Sea since the 1980s. This study aimed to assess eutrophication dynamics in the Romanian Exclusive Economic Zone from 2020 to 2022 using the Black Sea Eutrophication Assessment Tool (BEAST), an integrated approach to the causes and effects of eutrophication. Data were collected from 68 stations during five oceanographic expeditions, analysing 617 water samples for nutrients, chlorophyll *a*, zooplankton species *Noctiluca scintillans*, and dissolved oxygen. Additionally, 179 zoobenthic and 251 phytobenthic community samples were collected. The results indicate that coastal waters exhibit higher nutrient levels and algal blooms compared to offshore waters, necessitating significant reductions in nutrient concentrations to achieve good environmental status. In transitional waters, within the Danube Delta Biosphere Reserve, a 55% reduction in inorganic phosphorus and a 43% reduction in inorganic nitrogen concentrations are required, while coastal waters need reductions of 38% and 37%, respectively. The study highlights the need for improved wastewater treatment, stricter agricultural runoff controls, and continuous monitoring. Effective ecosystem-based management strategies, integrated coastal zone management, and international cooperation are essential to mitigate eutrophication and promote the long-term health of the Black Sea ecosystem.

Keywords: eutrophication; Black Sea; BEAST; nutrients; chlorophyll; macroalgae; zooplankton; *Noctiluca scintillans*; macrozoobenthos

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1. Introduction

Eutrophication—a process characterised by the excessive enrichment of water bodies with nutrients, often resulting in harmful algal blooms, oxygen depletion, and disruptions to marine biodiversity [1–3], fuelled by anthropogenic activities such as agricultural runoff, industrial discharge, and urbanisation [4–7]—is a longstanding issue in numerous seas worldwide, including the Baltic Sea [8–11], the North Sea [9], and Gulf of Mexico [12]. The Black Sea experienced a significant increase in eutrophication in the 1980–1990s [13,14], driven largely by nutrients Danube’s input from human activities such as agricultural runoff, industrial discharge, and urbanisation of the river’s basin [15–17].

In the 1960s, the Black Sea featured high productivity, with abundant pelagic fauna and extensive red algae fields, making it ideal for fish [18,19] and recognised as naturally eutrophicated due to continuous nutrient input from the Danube. Between 1950 and 1990, anthropogenic activities intensified in the Danube’s basin, causing significant

changes [20] and nitrogen loads rose from 400 kt/year to 900 kt/year, largely from agricultural sources, while phosphorus increased from 40 kt/year to 115 kt/year, primarily from human settlements [21,22]. These alterations, combined with climate variability, overfishing and invasive species triggered dramatic changes in the 1980s [23] with significant phytoplankton blooms and hypoxic bottom waters [24–28]. By the early 1990s, reduced nutrient loads signalled initial recovery signs, although with persistent dysfunctions [21]. Thus, in 2005, it appeared that the ecological degradation had settled into a quasi-stable state with yearly variations [29,30]. The consistently low zooplankton biomass diminished marine life, and the moderate presence of *Noctiluca scintillans* and jellyfish biomass signifies a compromised ecosystem [29,31,32]. The ecosystem functioned in an intermediate production state—neither as minimal and healthy as the pristine state nor as abundantly productive yet deteriorated as the eutrophic state characterised by the dominance of jellyfish and other opportunistic species [29,33,34], standing in contrast to the fish-dominated, healthy pristine state [35]. Consequently, the state should not be misinterpreted as a sign of recovery or ecological restoration of the north-western Black Sea shelf, contrary to suggestions by McQuatters-Gollop et al. (2008) [31,36]. A causal link between anthropogenic nutrient sources and the emergence of eutrophication symptoms is generally accepted [35]. However, cause-and-effect relationships are complex because coastal ecosystems respond to nutrient loading in various ways. System-specific attributes can act as filters that modulate responses to enrichment, and a complex array of direct and indirect interactions may occur [35]. In the Black Sea, the combined effects of nutrient loading and overfishing triggered a trophic cascade that altered the ecosystem’s structure and dynamics [36]. Additionally, other environmental degradation sources, such as toxic substances, overfishing, invasive species, climate changes, and natural variability, can confound these causal relationships [35].

Recent years (2018) have shown slight improvements in nutrients and algal bloom regimes. Still, the latest evaluation revealed the eutrophicated Romanian Black Sea [37] (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Evolution of eutrophication status in the Black Sea (1950–2017).

Currently, eutrophication remains a pressing issue in the Black Sea, with nutrient enrichment continuing to pose significant ecological and socio-economic challenges [13,16]. While efforts were made to reduce nutrient inputs in the Danube’s basin and improve water quality through initiatives like the Convention for Protection of the Black Sea against Pollution (1992) and the International Convention for the Protection of Danube River

(1994) together with European legislation (applicable for the two Black Sea's riparian European Member States—Romania and Bulgaria), the problem persists due to ongoing anthropogenic, potential cumulative pressures and climate change impacts [2,38].

The Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) [39] is the European Union's key legislation aimed at protecting marine environments and achieving "Good Environmental Status" (GES) of EU marine waters by 2020 and maintaining it thereafter. Adopted in June 2008, the directive includes, using 11 descriptors, various aspects of marine health, including biodiversity, invasive species, fisheries, food web, eutrophication, hydrological conditions, contaminants, noise, and marine litter [39]. The MSFD requires each EU member state to define what constitutes good environmental status for their marine waters. For eutrophication (descriptor 5), GES involves ensuring that nutrient concentrations and direct effects of nutrient enrichment (like algal blooms and oxygen depletion) are at levels that do not adversely affect the ecosystem [40]. Under the directive, member states must establish and implement coordinated monitoring programs for the ongoing assessment of their marine waters. These programs are designed to assess various descriptors for GES, including nutrient levels and indicators of eutrophication such as chlorophyll (a proxy for algal growth) concentration and dissolved oxygen levels. The directive promotes an integrated approach to marine ecosystem-based management, linking with other EU policies and directives such as the Water Framework Directive (WFD) and the Common Fisheries Policy [41,42]. This holistic approach ensures that measures taken under these policies do not contradict or destabilise efforts to combat eutrophication [43].

According to MSFD assessments, the most recent status of eutrophication in the Black Sea (2018) varies spatially and temporally, with transitional and coastal areas typically experiencing pronounced effects (non-GES). Algal blooms, reduced transparency, and changes in biodiversity patterns continue to be observed, highlighting the need for continued monitoring and management efforts to mitigate the impacts of eutrophication on the Black Sea ecosystem. Thus, understanding the spatial distribution and varying impacts of eutrophication within the Black Sea is not only a matter of scientific inquiry but also a pressing concern for sustainable coastal and marine management.

The purpose of this study is to obtain new data (2020–2022) regarding the causes and effects of eutrophication from the entire Romanian Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) and conduct a comprehensive assessment of eutrophication dynamics in the coastal and offshore waters of the Black Sea, utilising the Black Sea Eutrophication Assessment Tool (BEAST) as an integrated evaluation tool. By examining key indicators such as nutrient levels, algal proliferation, transparency, oxygen depletion, and biodiversity patterns from coastal and offshore marine units, the study aims to elucidate the spatial variability and differential impacts of eutrophication within the Black Sea ecosystem. Nutrient enrichment typically leads to increased phytoplankton primary production and the growth of short-lived macroalgae. As phytoplankton biomass rises, light penetration through the water column diminishes [1]. This reduction in light penetration, often measured as a decrease in water transparency (visibility) using a 'Secchi depth' instrument, can ultimately limit the colonisation depth of macroalgae and seagrasses [44]. Ecosystems generally respond to nutrient enrichment with a gradual shift towards (1) increased planktonic primary production relative to benthic production, (2) a dominance of microbial food webs over the traditional planktonic food chain from small to large organisms, (3) a predominance of non-siliceous phytoplankton species over diatom species, (4) a dominance of gelatinous zooplankton (jellyfish) over crustacean zooplankton, (5) increased sedimentation of organic matter to the seafloor, (6) near-seafloor oxygen depletion due to the oxygen consumption by degrading organic matter, ultimately leading to hypoxia or anoxia, and (7) the loss of higher life forms, including fish and bottom invertebrates, due to poor oxygen conditions. These changes can also be driven by organic matter loads from riverine or direct discharges [44].

The study provides new data for the current state of eutrophication in the Black Sea, a critical region facing escalating environmental and other challenges, including the recent war from Ukraine. Eutrophication is a complex phenomenon, thus by using an integrated

multidisciplinary approach to its assessment, the study seeks to contribute to the scientific understanding of nutrient dynamics and their ecological consequences in both coastal and offshore environments. Furthermore, the research aims to inform evidence-based policies and collaborative initiatives aimed at mitigating eutrophication effects and promoting the long-term resilience of the Black Sea ecosystem. Through interdisciplinary collaboration and informed decision-making, this study attempts to advance the collective efforts toward achieving sustainable marine conservation and coastal management in the Black Sea region. Overall, the study's focus on understanding and managing eutrophication in the Black Sea intersects with multiple SDGs related to environmental conservation, sustainable development, and climate action—SDG 14 (Life Below Water), SDG 15 (Life on Land), SDG 6 (Clean Water and Sanitation), SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities), and SDG 13 (Climate Action).

The study represents the first comprehensive assessment of eutrophication dynamics in both coastal and offshore waters of the Romanian Black Sea utilising the Black Sea Eutrophication Assessment Tool (BEAST). Thus, the purpose of this study is twofold: firstly, to elucidate how the intensity and impact of eutrophication differ between the coastal and offshore waters of the Black Sea, and secondly, to provide critical insights that can inform evidence-based policies and management strategies aimed at mitigating the adverse effects of eutrophication while promoting the long-term sustainability of marine ecosystems and associated socio-economic activities.

This study provides valuable insights into eutrophication in the Black Sea. By collecting new data during oceanographic cruises, the assessment of nutrients, algal proliferation, and biodiversity patterns in coastal and offshore waters is performed. Importantly, this work may help to establish a baseline for understanding the natural variability in the spatial distribution of nutrients and biological components. These findings contribute to effective management and conservation efforts by comparing the eutrophication status between coastal (anthropogenically changed) and offshore waters.

The current status of eutrophication research in the Black Sea is characterised by a deepened understanding of nutrient concentrations [44–47], algal blooms [28,48–50], and oxygen depletion [51–53], yet it is still evolving to incorporate more integrated and multidisciplinary approaches. The use of integrated tools, which bring together various data sources and methodologies, is adding significant value to research efforts by enhancing the ability to analyse, predict, and manage the phenomenon more effectively. Thus, BEAST was previously applied in European projects MISIS [54], ANEMONE [15] and national studies for different areas [37], but never for the entire EEZ of Romania's Black Sea. The tool is similar to the HELCOM Eutrophication Assessment Tool (HEAT) used in the Baltic Sea [55–58].

The main aim of this work is to assess eutrophication dynamics in the Black Sea, focusing on both coastal and offshore waters, utilising the Black Sea Eutrophication Assessment Tool (BEAST). Through comprehensive analysis, the study reveals significant discrepancies in eutrophication intensity between coastal and offshore zones.

Key conclusions highlight that coastal waters exhibit substantial eutrophication, characterised by elevated nutrient levels, increased algal proliferation, and reduced transparency compared to offshore areas. The findings underline the critical importance of targeted management strategies to address coastal eutrophication and protect the health and sustainability of the Black Sea ecosystem.

2. Materials and Methods

The study area is in the north-western Black Sea, in Romania's Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ). From June 2020 to September 2022, five oceanographic expeditions were conducted during the warm season with the research vessels "Steaua de Mare" and "Mare Nigrum" to survey two networks of 68 stations covering all reporting marine units (MRU) within the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (Figure 2). A total of 617 water samples were collected, and nutrient concentrations analysed for 463 samples, chlorophyll

a for 263 and the non-fodder zooplankton *Noctiluca scintillans* for 318 samples. Zoobenthic communities were analysed based on 179 samples collected from 55 stations in 2020 to 2022.

Figure 2. Study area map and network sampling stations in the Romanian Black Sea (EEZ).

Samples were collected and analysed according to specific methodologies [59–66] described in the Supplementary Materials (Table S1).

Romanian marine waters are classified into four marine reporting units (Figure 2):

- BLK_RO_RG_TT03—transitional waters (from baseline to and including 29 m isobath),
- BLK_RO_RG_CT—coastal waters (from the baseline to the 29 m isobath inclusive),
- BLK_RO_RG_MT01—marine waters (shelf)—from the 30 m isobath to the 200 m isobath,
- BLK_RO_RG_MT02—offshore waters—over the 200 m isobath.

Moreover, between 2020 and 2022, during the warm season (July and September), three dedicated expeditions were carried out to monitor phytobenthic communities (macroalgae and marine phanerogams). In total, 251 samples were collected from the coastal area between Midia Năvodari and Vama Veche (Figure 3), from depths between 0 and 8 m. The samples were analysed qualitatively (to draw up the species list) and quantitatively (wet biomass and abundance calculation). Specific indicators were subsequently applied to assess the ecological status of the coastal water body based on the biological elements macroalgae and marine phanerogams.

The main nutrient sources and pathways into the Romanian Black Sea primarily result from the Danube River, which carries substantial loads of nitrogen and phosphorus from agricultural runoff, industrial discharges, and urban wastewater [15]. Additionally, direct discharges from insufficiently treated wastewater from facilities such as Rompetrol, Constanta Nord, Constanta Sud, Eforie, and Mangalia significantly contribute to nutrient enrichment [67]. Agricultural runoff, urban runoff, industrial discharges, coastal tourism activities, and shipping operations also add to the nutrient load [68].

Figure 3. Study area map and macroalgae network sampling stations in the Romanian Black Sea coastal waters—2020–2022.

Methodology for Eutrophication Assessment

Descriptor 5 is defined in Annex I of the MSFD as “Human-induced eutrophication is minimised, especially adverse effects thereof, such as losses in biodiversity, ecosystem degradation, harmful algal blooms and oxygen deficiency in bottom waters” and is usually called Eutrophication. The criteria and indicators for D5 assessment should be synergistically considered. The overview of criteria, indicators, and thresholds (based on Commission Decision 848/2017—Descriptor 5) [69] and methods used for indicators, criteria evaluation and thresholds are described in the Supplementary Materials (Tables S2 and S3).

The present assessment considers principally the primary criteria—causes of eutrophication—nutrients (dissolved inorganic nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) (D5C1), direct effects of nutrient enrichment—chlorophyll *a* in the warm season (D5C2) and indirect effects—dissolved oxygen in bottom waters (D5C5) or macrofauna communities in benthic habitats (D5C8), where criterion D5C5 is not applicable due to the natural characteristics of the Black Sea (depths over 50 m). Of these, only D5C2 is a seasonally (summer) assessed criterion.

If the primary criteria do not fall under good ecological status, continue the assessment with the secondary criteria as follows: D5C3—harmful blooms with *Noctiluca scintillans*; D5C4—water transparency in the warm season; D5C6—opportunistic phytobenthic species with development in the warm season and D5C8—benthic communities. This last criterion also becomes primary if criterion D5C5 is not relevant (eligible).

The evaluation methodologies of each criterion are:

D5C1—Nutrient concentrations are assessed differently for marine regions. Thus, in transitional and coastal waters, the 75th percentile of concentrations of phosphate, nitrate, nitrite, and ammonium are compared with the maximum allowable concentrations with those from the updated Management Plan of the Danube River, Danube Delta, Dobrogea hydrographic area and coastal waters [24]. For marine waters, the assessment was performed by calculating the 75th percentile for phosphate concentrations representing dissolved inorganic phosphorus (DIP) and dissolved inorganic nitrogen (DIN—the sum of nitrate, nitrite, and ammonium) in surface waters and comparison with proposed threshold

values (GES) (Equation (1)) and recommended reduction percentage (Equation (2)). In both cases, the environmental status was established on the principle of 'OneOutAllOut', being a primary criterion.

$$Exceedance [\%] = Abs \left(\frac{Threshold\ value [\mu M] - 75th\ percentile [\mu M]}{Threshold\ value [\mu M]} \times 100 \right) \quad (1)$$

$$Reduction [\%] = \frac{75th\ percentile [\mu M] - Threshold\ value [\mu M]}{75th\ percentile [\mu M]} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

D5C2—Evaluation of chlorophyll *a* status for all marine regions is carried out by calculating the concentrations' 75th percentile corresponding to the surface layer (0–10 m) of all values and comparing with the proposed threshold values (GES). Environmental status is established on the 'OneOutAllOut' principle, a primary criterion.

D5C3—*Noctiluca scintillans* status was established by comparing the biomass with the threshold values established for the cold season (November to April) and warm season (May to October). The 'OneOutAllOut' principle is not considered being considered too restrictive. For the proportion method, it is considered that if at least 50% of the samples analysed for each season and marine region are in good status, then that region is in good status.

D5C4—The sea transparency assessment for transitional and coastal waters is performed by comparing all measured values with the minimum allowable value in national legislation. For marine waters, the assessment was carried out by calculating the 10th percentile for transparency measured in the warm season and comparing it with the proposed threshold value (GES). In both cases, ecological status shall be established on the principle of 'OneOutAllOut', a primary criterion.

D5C5—The criterion has no match in the WFD referring to dissolved oxygen in the waters at the water-sediment interface. In transitional and coastal waters, it is used only for stations with a depth of 20 m and in marine waters for the bathymetric strip 30–50 m, beyond (in the shelf and offshore area) being replaced by D5C8. The assessment is achieved by calculating the 10th percentile for dissolved oxygen concentrations and saturation in the warm season and comparing it with the proposed threshold value (GES). Ecological status shall be established on the principle of 'OneOutAllOut', a primary criterion.

D5C6—Calculate the proportion of opportunistic species biomass (ESG II) to total biomass at the level of each MRU coastal water station. The determined value shall then be reported to the threshold value. Good environmental status is considered when $ESG\ II < 40\%$.

D5C7—The Ecological Index (EI) is applied, a complex indicator based on the theory that anthropogenic stressors (e.g., eutrophication and/or pollution) change an ecosystem where perennial, habitat-forming species dominate, into a degraded ecosystem where opportunistic, nitrophilic algal species predominate. In terms of environmental tolerance, species included in ESG IA are the most sensitive to eutrophication conditions, followed by those included in ESG IB and ESG IC. This distribution according to the eutrophication gradient can be illustrated as follows: $ESG\ IA > ESG\ IB > ESG\ IC > ESG\ IIA > ESG\ IIB > ESG\ IICa > ESG\ IICb$. Seven categories of ecological classes allow each identified species to be classified:

ESG IA, ESG IB, ESG IC—perennial indicator species of areas generally included in good ecological status (regarding species of Phyllophora, Cystoseira, Zostera);

ESG IIA—species with a high adaptability;

ESG IIB, ESG IICa, ESG IICb—opportunistic species, capable of growing in eutrophicated areas with a high reproductive capacity (species of *Ceramium*, *Ulva*, *Cladophora*), whose dominance defines areas included in poor ecological status).

Subsequently, several specific formulae are applied [70] and the obtained EI value is related to the threshold value. Good ecological status is considered when the Ecological Index (EI) > 6 .

D5C8—The status of large benthal habitats based on the normalised M-AMBI index*(n) [71] shall be assessed by averaging the value of the index per monitoring station throughout the assessment period. The proportions method is used to determine the total status of each water body (unit of reporting) because the mean can distort the result and mask the problems. The ‘OneOutAllOut’ principle in the WFD is not taken into account as it was considered too restrictive. As regards the proportions method, it is considered that if at least 75% of the samples analysed on each habitat type are in good status, then that habitat is in good condition; The same principle is used to assess the quality of each water body.

An integrated assessment tool, based on HEAT, used in the Baltic Sea (HELCOM, 2018) is BEAST (Black Sea Eutrophication Assessment Tool). BEAST was developed within the framework of the Baltic2Black project [54] in which the Black Sea (BSC) and Baltic Sea Commissions (HELCOM) were partners. At the regional level, it is proposed as an evaluation tool within the regional integrated monitoring program, the Black Sea Integrated Monitoring and Assessment Programme (BSIMAP). BEAST is based on three levels classified into C1—causes of eutrophication, C2—direct effects and C3—indirect effects of eutrophication. Each criterion is described by a set of indicators. Evaluation results represent the ratio EUT_Ratio as the ratio of the current value to the threshold value and are included, depending on the indicator’s contribution, in a qualitative response: Very good, Good, Moderate, Poor, and Bad. Among the criteria, BEAST uses the “OneOutAllOut” principle. For a better visualisation of the data, we transformed the qualitative results into quantitative ones, giving the coefficients 1—very good; 2—good; 3—moderate; 4—poor; 5—bad. Thus, the boundary between “good” and “moderate” becomes the limit for establishing good environmental status (GES).

Due to the spatial and temporal fragmentation of indicators, a set of basic indicators was chosen, considered only for the warm season (May–September), as follows:

- Causes—concentrations of nutrients given equal weight under the criterion—25% each in transitional and coastal waters (phosphate, nitrate, nitrite, ammonium) and 50% each in marine waters (dissolved inorganic phosphorus and dissolved inorganic nitrogen);
- Direct Effects—Chlorophyll concentrations *a* and Transparency are given equal importance (50%);
- Indirect effects—Dissolved oxygen saturation of bottom waters.

The data were processed using MS Excel 365, Primer [72], Statistica (TIBCO Software Version 14.0.1.25) [73], ArcGIS Desktop 10.7 software [74], and Ocean Data View (ODV) version 5.6.5 [75]. Distribution maps in ArcGIS were generated through inverse distance weighting (IDW) interpolation, a method that calculates cell values based on a weighted combination of nearby sampling points.

3. Results

3.1. Criterion Assessment

3.1.1. Nutrients in Seawater (D5C1)

The analysis of dissolved nutrient concentrations was carried out through measurements of dissolved inorganic phosphorus (phosphate, PO₄) and inorganic nitrogen (nitrate, NO₃, nitrite, NO₂, ammonium, NH₄ and their sum, DIN) in surface (0 m) waters. The dataset included 145 observations for each parameter, against which established threshold values were compared (Table 1). The statistical data reveal significant variability in nutrient concentrations across different parameters. For example, phosphate levels show a relatively low average and median but have a high maximum, indicating intermittent spikes in concentration. Similarly, the inorganic nitrogenous compounds exhibit a broad range of values—nitrate and ammonium showed a considerable spread of their concentrations, reflected in high standard deviations thus underlining the episodic nature of nutrient input, likely influenced by both anthropogenic activities and natural processes.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of nutrient concentrations in surface seawater—Black Sea, 2020–2022.

Variable	N	Mean [μM]	Median [μM]	Minimum [μM]	Maximum [μM]	75th Percentile [μM]	Std. Dev. [μM]
Phosphate, PO_4	145	0.38	0.11	0.01	14.26	0.35	1.27
Nitrite, NO_2	145	2.09	0.17	0.01	23.15	1.64	4.37
Nitrate, NO_3	145	5.10	1.77	0.01	70.96	4.79	9.71
Ammonium, NH_4	145	4.90	2.31	0.01	25.02	7.50	5.48
Dissolved Inorganic Nitrogen, DIN	145	12.13	7.81	1.31	72.54	16.09	13.06

3.1.2. Transitional Waters (BLK-RO-RG-TT03)

The nutrient levels in the waters directly influenced by the Danube River were notably high, preventing the GES achievement. The 75th percentile (Table 2) indicates a non-GES status across all parameters, signifying that the concentrations regularly surpass the values defining a healthy marine environment. The data show substantial exceedances in inorganic phosphorus (PO_4) levels, which surpass the threshold by 122%, and in all inorganic nitrogen compounds—nitrite (NO_2), nitrate (NO_3), and ammonium (NH_4)—which exceed their respective thresholds by 492%, 68%, and 75%. Therefore, achieving a reduction of 55% in inorganic phosphorus and an average reduction of 43% (83% NO_2 , 13% NO_3 , and 43% NH_4) in inorganic nitrogen concentrations would be beneficial to achieve the GES in transitional waters.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of nutrient concentrations in surface seawater—TT03-Transitional waters, 2020–2022.

Variable	N	Mean [μM]	Median [μM]	Minimum [μM]	Maximum [μM]	75th Percentile [μM]	Threshold Value [μM]	Std. Dev. [μM]
Phosphate, PO_4	16	0.69	0.77	0.04	1.26	1.00	0.45	0.39
Nitrite, NO_2	16	4.35	1.86	0.01	17.97	7.10	1.20	5.47
Nitrate, NO_3	16	8.69	5.17	0.01	25.75	13.43	8.00	8.11
Ammonium, NH_4	16	7.40	6.37	0.01	20.34	12.50	7.14	6.27
Dissolved Inorganic Nitrogen, DIN	16	20.29	18.14	6.88	41.46	28.97	37.50	11.24

The results revealed a persistent nutrient pollution problem in the area, particularly emphasising the extreme deviation of nitrite levels from intensive agriculture runoff [76], which are nearly five times their GES threshold. The high variability and extreme values, as indicated by the standard deviations and maximum values, suggest episodic pollution events and consistent riverine input of nutrients, from point (wastewater discharges and industrial activities upstream) and diffuse sources—agricultural runoff.

3.1.3. Coastal Waters (BLK_RO_RG_CT)

Moving south from the transitional waters, the coastal waters continue to show signs of potential eutrophication, having not yet achieved Good Environmental Status (GES) for any nutrient indicators (Table 3). The most substantial overloads were observed for the inorganic nitrogen forms. The standard deviations and maximum values for each nutrient parameter are high, suggesting not only a widespread presence of the nutrients but also periodic extreme spikes, likely driven by episodic discharges or runoff events. The maximum concentrations of nitrate are particularly alarming, indicating severe episodes of nutrient pollution from sewage and manure, soil erosion and fertilisers [77]. The average concentrations and 75th percentile significantly exceed the thresholds set for achieving

GES being indicative of eutrophication, confirming systemic issues with water quality management in the coastal areas. Therefore, achieving a reduction of 38% in inorganic phosphorus and an average reduction of 37% (43% NO₂, 38% NO₃, and 31% NH₄) in inorganic nitrogen concentrations would be beneficial for a good status of eutrophication in Romanian coastal waters.

Table 3. Descriptive statistics of nutrient concentrations in the surface seawater—CT—Coastal waters, 2020–2022.

Variable	N	Mean [μM]	Median [μM]	Minimum [μM]	Maximum [μM]	75th Percentile [μM]	Threshold Value [μM]	Std. Dev. [μM]
Phosphate, PO ₄	35	0.83	0.20	0.01	14.26	0.48	0.30	2.49
Nitrite, NO ₂	35	4.08	1.33	0.01	23.15	4.53	1.20	6.32
Nitrate, NO ₃	35	10.29	4.99	0.01	70.96	11.63	8.00	15.62
Ammonium, NH ₄	35	7.28	5.59	0.01	22.97	11.47	7.14	5.95
Dissolved Inorganic Nitrogen, DIN	35	21.36	16.56	4.86	72.54	25.63	13.50	16.48

3.1.4. Shelf Waters (BLK_RO_RG_MT01)

In shelf waters, GES was not achieved in only a small proportion and for minor exceedances of dissolved inorganic phosphorus and nitrogen concentrations (Table 4). This suggests that the area maintains nutrient concentrations within acceptable limits favourable to healthy marine ecosystems. The standard deviations indicate variability in nutrient concentrations across the marine waters, with some parameters experiencing higher variability (NO₃, NH₄, DIN) than others (PO₄, NO₂). This variability may be influenced by factors such as local hydrodynamics, nutrient inputs from various sources, and wind and currents regimes. The analysis underscores the generally “good” status of marine waters, with only minor deviations preventing the achievement of GES for certain localised areas, usually situated on the Northern side which suggests the potential influence of other rivers from the NW Black Sea.

Table 4. Descriptive statistics of nutrient concentrations in the surface seawater—MT01—Shelf marine waters, 2020–2022.

Variable	N	Mean [μM]	Median [μM]	Minimum [μM]	Maximum [μM]	75th Percentile [μM]	Threshold Value [μM]	Std. Dev. [μM]
Phosphate, PO ₄	76	0.18	0.05	0.01	1.33	0.27	0.23	0.27
Nitrite, NO ₂	76	1.18	0.09	0.01	15.76	0.57	Na *	2.79
Nitrate, NO ₃	76	3.26	1.52	0.01	44.24	2.51	Na	5.91
Ammonium, NH ₄	76	3.85	1.65	0.01	20.80	7.09	Na	4.47
Dissolved Inorganic Nitrogen, DIN	76	8.12	4.22	1.31	50.02	11.32	10.50	9.21

* Na—not available.

3.1.5. Offshore Marine Waters (BLK_RO_RG_MT02)

The assessment of marine waters in the Romanian offshore area represents a significant milestone as it marks the first evaluation since the implementation of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) in 2008. Concerning nutrient levels, offshore waters were in GES (Table 5). While phosphate, nitrite, and nitrate concentrations generally indicate the GES, ammonium and, consequently, DIN data, indicate potential pollution events or natural upwellings that may compromise water quality. This result emphasises the considerable impact that coastal regions and terrestrial sources have in delivering nutrients to the marine ecosystem.

On the other hand, nutrients in offshore waters exhibit the highest concentrations in the water column functioning as a nutrient sink and as a source during the upwelling events. In offshore waters, nutrient dynamics differ significantly from coastal environments, exhibiting some unique characteristics (Table 6, Figure 4). Here, the highest concentrations of phosphate, nitrite and nitrate are found under the deep chlorophyll maximum layer (DCM) in the water column. At greater depths, the water column acts as a nutrient sink for ammonium, which reaches its maximum at the bottom (Figure 4). Higher concentrations of ammonium and phosphate at deeper levels primarily due to the downward transport of organic materials, such as dead phytoplankton, faecal pellets, and detritus [46,78–81] may indicate areas of nutrient accumulation or specific biological and chemical processes occurring at these depths. These peaks could indicate potential zones for algal growth if these nutrients are upwelled to the photic zone (Figure 4). As these materials decompose, they release nutrients back into the water, which accumulate at these lower levels because of the limited light and colder temperatures, reducing the rate of biological uptake and decomposition [79,80,82–86]. The accumulation of nutrients in deep waters is a critical component of the oceanic nutrient cycle, effectively removing them from the surface waters where most biological productivity occurs, thereby impacting the availability of nutrients in the upper layers [87,88].

Figure 4. Nutrients water column (0–500 m) profile—Offshore Romanian Black Sea waters—2020–2022 (the red spot represents the station for water column distributions (red lines) for NO₂, NH₄, PO₄, NO₃).

Conversely, these nutrient-rich deep waters can become a significant source of nutrients during upwelling events [89]. Upwelling occurs when wind patterns and ocean currents bring deeper, colder, and nutrient-dense waters to the surface [90–92]. This process

can change the nutrient dynamics of surface water, providing a fresh supply of essential nutrients like nitrogen, phosphorus, and silica [89,92]. These nutrients fuel primary productivity, often leading to phytoplankton blooms that can significantly alter the local marine ecosystem.

Table 5. Descriptive statistics of nutrient concentrations in the surface seawater—MT02—Offshore marine waters, 2020–2022.

Variable	N	Mean [μM]	Median [μM]	Minimum [μM]	Maximum [μM]	75th Percentile [μM]	Threshold Value [μM]	Std. Dev. [μM]
Phosphate, PO_4	18	0.06	0.03	0.01	0.35	0.06	0.23	0.09
Nitrite, NO_2	18	0.07	0.06	0.01	0.27	0.07	Na	0.06
Nitrate, NO_3	18	1.26	1.24	0.83	1.89	1.44	Na	0.32
Ammonium, NH_4	18	2.51	0.93	0.01	25.02	1.79	Na	5.70
Dissolved Inorganic Nitrogen, DIN	18	3.83	2.30	1.60	26.12	2.81	10.50	5.64

Table 6. Descriptive statistics of nutrient concentrations in the water column (0–500 m)—MT02—Offshore marine waters, 2020–2022.

	N	Mean [μM]	Median [μM]	Minimum [μM]	Maximum [μM]	75th Percentile [μM]	Std. Dev. [μM]
Phosphate, PO_4	79	1.15	0.26	0.01	6.94	1.25	1.92
Nitrite, NO_2	79	0.10	0.06	0.01	0.42	0.13	0.11
Nitrate, NO_3	79	2.20	1.68	0.20	6.62	2.77	1.49
Ammonium, NH_4	79	4.47	1.08	0.01	47.72	2.06	10.25
Dissolved Inorganic Nitrogen, DIN	79	6.78	3.34	1.66	49.45	5.94	9.98

3.1.6. Chlorophyll *a* in the Water Column (D5C2)

Chlorophyll is commonly used as an indicator of phytoplankton biomass and overall primary productivity, which are often enhanced by nutrient inputs due to eutrophication [88,93]. Considering the distribution of chlorophyll *a* concentrations from the water column to the layer of maximum concentration during the warm seasons of 2020–2022, three areas with elevated concentrations are noticeable. These areas include the neighbourhood of the Danube mouths, nearby Constanța city (specifically the port area), and the southernmost littoral (Mangalia—Vama Veche). Thus, transitional and coastal waters exhibit higher and more variable chlorophyll *a* concentrations, suggesting greater susceptibility to eutrophication. In contrast, offshore waters show low and stable chlorophyll *a* levels, consistent with their oligotrophic nature. The transitional waters' mean suggests moderate to high chlorophyll *a* levels but high variability (standard deviation), revealing significant phytoplankton biomass peaks (Table 6).

The average chlorophyll *a* concentration in coastal waters is lower than transitional with an extremely variable range suggesting episodic high eutrophication (Table 6). Thus, the highest concentration of 31.36 $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$ was recorded at the Constanța Sud 5 m station in the vicinity of the biggest wastewater treatment plant (WWTP). Concentrations decrease with the distance from the shore, with shelf water sporadic high values being present with most offshore stations of concentrations below 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$.

In all marine reporting units, GES was achieved with percentages of 93% (of $N = 15$ stations) in transitional waters, 85% in coastal waters (of $N = 27$ stations), 95% in marine waters from the northern area (of $N = 39$ stations), and 95% in marine waters from the southern area (of $N = 78$ stations). No threshold for offshore waters is available yet. Consequently, all four assessed marine-reporting regions achieved GES (Table 7).

Table 7. Descriptive statistics of chlorophyll *a* concentrations—Romanian Black Sea 2020–2022.

Marine Reporting Unit	N	Mean (µg/L)	Median (µg/L)	Minimum (µg/L)	Maximum (µg/L)	75th Percentile (µg/L)	Threshold Value (µg/L)	Std. Dev. (µg/L)
All	346	1.95	0.66	0.06	31.36	1.42		3.58
Transitional waters	25	6.12	4.60	0.42	14.95	10.21	11.88	4.71
Coastal waters	64	3.55	1.64	0.28	31.36	3.34	5.97	5.18
Shelf waters—Northern area	68	2.29	0.60	0.06	16.84	1.86	4.11	3.76
Shelf waters—Southern area	137	0.86	0.53	0.11	14.40	0.77	2.79	1.63
Offshore waters	52	0.40	0.33	0.18	1.04	0.53	Na	0.22

The data on chlorophyll *a* concentrations across various Romanian Black Sea marine units highlight the impact of the introduction of nutrient pressure, particularly in transitional, coastal and northern shelf waters where mean concentrations are significantly higher (6.12 µg/L, 3.55 µg/L, and 2.29 µg/L, respectively) compared to the southern shelf and the offshore areas. The data also show greater variability and extremely high peak levels (up to 31.36 µg/L), suggesting substantial phytoplankton blooms likely driven by nutrient runoff from urbanisation (wastewater treatment plants, sewage, insufficiently treated waters). In contrast, the significantly lower chlorophyll *a* levels in offshore waters (mean of 0.40 µg/L) indicate less nutrient availability and lower primary productivity, pointing to the localised nature of nutrient enrichment and its pronounced effects near population centers and river mouths (Table 7).

The average phytoplankton abundances during the warm seasons of 2020–2022 revealed blooms (over 10^6 cells/L) in two regions of significant growth: near the Danube's mouths and along the southern littoral, as was expected from chlorophyll *a* variability data. Particularly, in the transitional waters, all profiles ranged from 1.5×10^6 cells/L to 3.7×10^6 cells/L. The highest densities in coastal waters were recorded at the Mangalia 1 station, with maximum values reaching 5.7×10^6 cells/L. In marine waters, concentrations exceeded 10^6 cells/L at several stations in the Northern shelf with abundances between 1.1×10^6 and 2.4×10^6 cells/L, as well as stations in the Southern shelf, which showed 1.3×10^6 to 2×10^6 cells/L.

3.1.7. *Noctiluca scintillans* Biomass (D5C3)

In the case of the “*Noctiluca scintillans* Biomass” indicator, GES was achieved in a proportion of 74% in transitional waters and 84% in marine waters (Figure 5) while in coastal waters, GES was only for 43% of stations, thus being considered non-GES. The mean biomass for all areas combined is relatively high at 298.2 mg/m³, with a very high standard deviation of 822.3 mg/m³, indicating a wide range of values that could reflect different levels of nutrient availability, human activity impact, or ecological responses across sampled areas (Table 8). Lower mean and median of *Noctiluca scintillans* biomass were observed in transitional waters compared to coastal waters but higher than in shelf and offshore waters. The moderate values suggest a mix of influences, possibly from terrestrial and open sea sources. The relatively high standard deviation (468.8 mg/m³) indicates significant variability as already found for nutrients and chlorophyll levels. The significantly higher mean (963.1 mg/m³) and median (570.6 mg/m³) are indicative of substantial *Noctiluca* biomass and potentially higher nutrient availability or pollution levels in the coastal waters. The maximum value (8646 mg/m³) is exceptionally high, an extreme, suggesting episodic harmful blooms possibly driven by nutrient runoff from Romanian southern littoral coastal settlements (Vama Veche). Much lower mean (2.51 mg/m³) and median (0.9 mg/m³) in the shelf waters suggest less available nutrients or different ecological dynamics compared to more impacted waters from the coastal area. The smallest range and standard deviation indicate more stable conditions but with very low *Noctiluca* biomass. However, in offshore waters, a moderate standard deviation (57.3 mg/m³) implies variability but to a lesser degree than other marine units.

Figure 5. Ecological status of *Noctiluca scintillans* biomass indicator—Romanian Black Sea 2020–2022.

Table 8. Descriptive statistics of *Noctiluca scintillans* Biomass (mg/m^3)—Romanian Black Sea 2020–2022.

Marine Reporting Unit	N	Mean [mg/m^3]	Median [mg/m^3] (Percentile 50th)	Minimum [mg/m^3]	Maximum [mg/m^3]	Threshold Value [mg/m^3]	Std. Dev. [mg/m^3]
All	318	298.2	20.0	0.0	8646.0		822.3
Transitional waters	15	282.9	96.1	3.5	1362.5	240	468.8
Coastal waters	35	963.1	570.6	0.0	8646.0	350	1505.4
Shelf waters	211	2.51	0.9	0.0	25.02	240	736.4
Offshore waters	57	19.4	2.6	0.0	337.2	240	57.3

Certain investigations have explored the significance of *N. scintillans* in environments abundant in nutrients. This dinoflagellate can potentially serve as a vital contributor and supplier of nutrients, given its capability for regeneration, resulting in notable amounts of ammonium and inorganic phosphorus supplied to primary phytoplankton production [94]. It is worth noting that, in coastal waters, nutrient concentrations did not reach GES, potentially fostering the excessive proliferation of this dinoflagellate, thereby contributing to a poor status within this marine reporting unit.

3.1.8. Photic Limit (Transparency) of the Water Column (D5C4)

As indicated by the data (Table 8), the variability in seawater transparency of different areas of the Romanian Black Sea is exponential (Figure 6) and significantly ($r = -0.62$, $p < 0.005$) linked to the effects of eutrophication, phytoplankton blooms approximated by chlorophyll *a* (confidence 95%) (Figure 7). Thus, in transitional and coastal waters, significantly lower mean transparencies (2 m and 4 m, respectively) suggest high levels of nutrient runoff that stimulate phytoplankton growth, reducing clarity due to increased biomass. The sharp decrease in transparency in these areas, compared to the clearer shelf and offshore waters with average transparency reaching up to 13m, underlines the impact of localised nutrient enrichment near river discharges and urban coastal zones. Such conditions in nearshore waters not only affect water quality but also disrupt marine ecosystems by altering light penetration, which is crucial for aquatic life. The offshore area was the singular unit where GES was observed (Table 9).

Figure 6. Scatterplot of chlorophyll a [µg/L] and transparency [m] (SDD) of Romanian Black Sea—2020–2022 (red lines represent the trendline and the confidence interval).

Figure 7. Spatial variability of bottom waters content in dissolved oxygen (saturation, % (L) and mg/L(R)) in the Romanian Black Sea grouped by marine reporting units (MRU)—2020–2022.

Table 9. Descriptive statistics of transparency (m)—Romanian Black Sea, 2020–2022.

Marine Reporting Unit	N	Mean [m]	Median [m]	Minimum [m]	Maximum [m]	10th Percentile, [m]	Threshold Value [m]	Std. Dev. [m]
All	94	8	9	1	21	2		4.60
Transitional waters	9	2	1	1	4	1	2.3	0.98
Coastal waters	12	4	4	2	7	3	5.6	1.65
Shelf waters	58	8	9	2	16	4	6.8	3.77
Offshore waters	15	13	13	10	21	10	6.8	3.08

3.1.9. Dissolved Oxygen in the Bottom of the Water Column (D5C5)

The variability of the oxygen regime is influenced by multiple factors that exert opposing effects. Factors contributing to the enrichment of dissolved oxygen include the air and seawater temperature, flow patterns of currents and winds, surface contact with the atmosphere promoting a well-oxygenated layer, and the photosynthetic activities of marine vegetation (phytoplankton and macrophytes). Conversely, factors leading to reduced dissolved oxygen concentrations, which are more numerous and diverse, encompassing increased air and water temperatures, interactions of supersaturated water masses with the atmosphere, respiration of aquatic plant and animal organisms, various biological and chemical processes including the reactions of reducing agents, dissolved or particulate organic matter, sediments, enzymatic processes, bacterial oxidation of organic matter, etc., and stratification of water masses. During the warm seasons of 2020–2022, bottom waters (N = 55) of stations with a maximum depth of 50 m exhibited good oxygenation. Across all zones, the dissolved oxygen levels are generally above the critical level (typically 6 mg/L for most species), suggesting a healthy aquatic environment beneficial to marine life. The dissolved oxygen saturation indicates that the waters are mostly well-oxygenated, although variations are present. Transitional waters show slightly more variability in both concentration and saturation of dissolved oxygen. Coastal waters show slightly higher oxygen concentrations and saturation than shelf areas, which might be influenced by geographical features for water mixing. The 10th percentile of all recorded values was 7.7 mg/L, with 76.1% values corresponding to GES. No instances were observed where oxygen saturation fell below 60% (Table 10 and Figure 7). Consequently, the ecological status based on this criterion is considered good. Although not evaluated for this criterion, data for offshore waters were provided (Table 10). The data indicate a gradient in oxygen availability from relatively abundant and stable conditions in coastal and transitional waters to variable and often critically low levels in shelf and offshore waters due to the Black Sea natural features, making the criterion non-eligible at bottom depths higher than 50 m. The observed outliers (Figure 7), particularly in the shelf and offshore zones, likely reflect the natural anoxic waters in the Black Sea. These low oxygen levels are consistent with the region's known stratification and presence of anoxic deep waters. While the transitional and coastal waters show higher oxygen levels with fewer outliers, the deeper and more offshore areas exhibit the characteristic low oxygen conditions associated with hypoxic conditions preceding anoxia [95].

Table 10. Descriptive statistics of bottom dissolved oxygen concentration and saturation—Romanian Black Sea, 2020–2022.

MarineReporting Unit	N	Mean	Median	Minimum	Maximum	10th Percentile	Threshold Value	Std. Dev.
All, O ₂ [mg/L]	121	6.52	7.74	0.14	10.59	0.77		3.09
All, O ₂ [%]	119	64.36	76.10	1.67	117.4	7.40		31.51
Transitional waters, O ₂ [mg/L]	10	8.40	8.18	7.16	10.40	7.33		1.03
Transitional waters, O ₂ [%]	10	83.85	81.30	68.50	108.00	70.25	5 mg/L	12.98
Coastal waters, O ₂ [mg/L]	20	8.93	9.12	7.56	10.59	7.80	60%	0.79
Coastal waters, O ₂ [%]	19	94.21	93.70	76.30	117.4	77.80		11.57
Shelf waters, O ₂ [mg/L]	80	6.36	7.41	0.17	10.01	9.13		2.93
Shelf waters, O ₂ [%]	79	61.41	70.10	1.67	98.90	87.20		28.64
Offshore waters, O ₂ [mg/L]	11	1.61	1.01	0.14	5.86	0.28	Not	1.65
Offshore waters, O ₂ [%]	11	16.30	9.80	4.07	56.80	5.10	eligible	15.47

3.1.10. Opportunistic Macroalgae of Benthic Habitats (D5C6)

Due to their high reproductive potential and rapid growth rate, opportunistic species adopt a development strategy that favours their proliferation, often at the expense of perennial species, by exploiting the abundant nutrients in seawater [96]. This sometimes results in their explosive growth during the warm season. Throughout the study (2020–2022, warm

season), opportunistic species, primarily *Ulva* spp., *Cladophora* spp., and *Ceramium* spp., generally exhibited higher biomasses within the 0–3 m bathymetric stripe. Southern Coastal waters between Agigea and Costinești (areas with high nutrient levels) witnessed a quantitative dominance of these opportunistic species. Overall, the biomass of opportunistic tolerant species (ESG II) constituted 23% of the total algal biomass. Comparing this proportion to the threshold value (ESG II < 40%), GES was achieved. Based on the indicator “Proportion of the biomass of opportunistic tolerant species (ESG II) from the total biomass”, a good status was also achieved, with a percentage of 54% for GES (Figures 8 and 9).

Figure 8. The proportion of opportunistic tolerant species (ESG II) and sensitive species (ESG I).

Figure 9. Assessment of the ecological status of coastal waters based on the biomass of opportunistic tolerant species (ESG II) from the total biomass, Romanian Black Sea, 2020–2022.

3.1.11. Macrophyte Communities (D5C7)

In the context of the Ecological Index (EI) indicator, serving as the baseline for assessing the ecological status of coastal waters GES was not accomplished, reaching only 44% (Figure 10). The EI values varied across coastal waters depending on the species composition, with peak values primarily observed towards the southern Romanian littoral, attributed to the prevalence of sensitive species classified under the ESG I category. The average Ecological Index (EI) value was 4.085, falling below the established threshold value for GES (EI > 6) (Table 11). Consequently, the ecological status based on this criterion is non-GES.

Figure 10. Ecological status of coastal waters based on the Ecological Index (EI), Romanian Black Sea, 2020–2022.

Table 11. Descriptive statistics for Ecological Index (EI)—Romanian Black Sea, 2020–2022.

Statistic	Ecological Index (EI)
Minimum	0.022
Maximum	10.000
First Quartile	0.831
Median	1.781
Third Quartile	7.908
Mean	4.085
Standard deviation (n – 1)	3.696

3.1.12. Macrofaunal Communities of Benthic Habitats (D5C8)

Benthic communities were evaluated based on broad habitat types, disregarding marine reporting units due to their mismatch in this context. Consequently, samples collected during the period 2020–2022 were scrutinised according to established threshold values for the infralittoral, circalittoral, and deep circalittoral (or offshore) mobile sediment habitats for the multiparametric indicator M-AMBI*(n) [71]. Special attention was directed towards the deep circalittoral zone, where fewer samples had been collected in preceding years.

The primary animal communities across major habitat types in the Romanian marine area were delineated through non-metric Multi-Dimensional Scaling (n-MDS) analysis conducted using PRIMER v.7 software (Figure 11). The analysis illustrates the clustering of communities across the benthic broad habitat types in infralittoral, circalittoral, and deep circalittoral zones. Notably, in the latter, the broader dispersion of communities is attributed to the various depth intervals from which samples were collected and analysed, ranging between 50 m and 140 m bottom depth.

Consequently, benthic communities within the infralittoral sedimentary habitats generally exhibited good ecological conditions. However, exceptions were noted in the Sulina (10 m) and Mangalia (20 m) areas, where EQR M-AMBI(n) values, though not indicative of good condition, were still in proximity to the threshold value (Figure 12).

The communities inhabiting circalittoral sediments generally exhibited good ecological status, as indicated by the EQR M-AMBI(n) values. However, an exception was observed at Portița (30–35 m), where the criteria for good conditions were not met in 2020 (Figure 13).

In the deep circalittoral zones, the situation becomes more complex. Here, due to the extensive depth ranges, distinct communities emerge, necessitating different thresholds to distinguish between GES and non-GES conditions. Consequently, when using the threshold values of the M-AMBI(n) index established for deep circalittoral mixed sediments with *Modiolula phaseolina*, beyond depths of 90–95 m, GES is not achieved due to a significant reduction in species diversity. As a result, it is observed that benthic ecological conditions are poor at all stations with considerable depths. Ideally, these stations should be excluded

from the assessment or evaluated against different thresholds; however, further data are required to establish alternative thresholds for communities at such depths.

Figure 11. Benthic broad habitat types based on n-MDS, Romania Black Sea, 2020–2022.

Figure 12. Ecological status of the macrozoobenthic communities on the infralittoral sediments based on EQR M-AMBI(n), Romania Black Sea, 2020–2022 (red bars represent the non-GES status).

Offshore stations (bottom depths exceeding 100 m) are inhabited by distinct organism communities with substantially lower diversity. This is primarily attributed to the low concentration of dissolved oxygen, as these areas are situated near the anoxic zone (sub-oxic zone). Overall, only 67% of the deep circalittoral communities exhibit good environmental status, which would characterise the entire area as being in poor ecological condition. If stations with bottom depths exceeding 100 m are excluded, then the proportion of those in good condition increases to 86% based on EQR M-AMBI(n) (Figure 14a,b).

Figure 13. Ecological status of the macrozoobenthic communities on the circalittoral sediments based on EQR M-AMBI(n), Romania Black Sea, 2020–2022 (red bar represent the non-GES status).

(a)

(b)

Figure 14. (a) Ecological status of macrozoobenthic communities on deep circalittoral sediments based on EQR M-AMBI(n), Romania Black Sea, 2020–2022. (b) Ecological status of macrozoobenthic communities on deep circalittoral sediments excluding communities beyond 100 m depth based on EQR M-AMBI(n), Romania Black Sea, 2020–2022.

3.1.13. Black Sea Eutrophication Assessment Tool—BEAST

BEAST findings comprised of 62 .xslm files, each containing assessments of eutrophication quality classes categorised as high, good, moderate, poor, and bad (Figure 15).

Figure 15. Black Sea Eutrophication Assessment Tool (BEAST) platform—example.

To enhance the analysis, representation, and visualisation, each quality class was assigned a numerical value based on Table 12.

Table 12. BEAST quality status associated with quality classes.

BEAST Result	BEAST Class	Environmental Status (MSFD)
High	1	GES
Good	2	
Moderate	3	Non-GES
Poor	4	
Bad	5	

The use of the BEAST (Black Sea Eutrophication Assessment Tool) revealed that during the 2020–2022 warm seasons, Romanian waters in the Black Sea achieved good environmental status at approximately 50% of the stations (out of the total), roughly encompassing 59% of the area (km²) within the Romanian waters of the Black Sea (EEZ) (Figure 16). Overall, there appears to be a slight improvement in the area covered by GES compared to the preceding reporting period (2018), likely due to the inclusion of the offshore marine region in the assessment. Still, transitional, coastal, and northern shelf waters exhibit the highest levels of eutrophication highlighted by different indicators, too. In coastal waters, achieving good conditions throughout the entire southern region proves challenging due to the influence of wastewater treatment plants in the Constanța Sud, Eforie, and Mangalia areas, as well as the port areas of Constanța and Mangalia. A deterioration in ecological condition is observed in the southernmost profiles of Mangalia and Vama Veche.

Figure 16. Spatial variability of the eutrophication in the Romanian Black Sea, 2020–2022.

The marine shelf waters, particularly on the mentioned profiles from the coastal region up to the 50–60 m isobaths, and even more extensively (80–90 m) in the Mangalia area, are characterised by an eutrophicated state.

In contrast, offshore marine waters exhibit a very good state, with no visible influence from anthropogenic pressures associated with the introduction of nutrients and organic matter.

4. Discussion

The nutrients input to the Black Sea, primarily through sources such as the Danube River and various urban and industrial point sources like wastewater treatment plants, sewage, insufficiently treated waters, and industrial and port areas, represent an important pressure at the Black Sea's Romanian littoral. Nutrients from agricultural runoff, urban waste, and industrial discharges enrich the coastal and transitional waters. Inorganic nitrogen forms like nitrite (NO_2), nitrate (NO_3), and ammonium (NH_4) are found in elevated levels due to these contributions. This study reveals that the pressure of nutrient inputs extends even to the shelf areas of the Black Sea, with impacts observed up to isobaths of 50–60 m and even 80 m in the southernmost littoral (Mangalia) serving as the primary fuel for the eutrophication process (Figures 17 and 18).

Surface nutrient concentrations exhibit strong correlations among themselves, as well as with chlorophyll *a* water column average levels (Figure 19), indicating that areas with higher concentrations of nutrients tend to have higher concentrations of chlorophyll *a*. This relationship highlights the role of nutrients in fuelling phytoplankton blooms. The correlation with salinity is considered information regarding the potential pathway of nutrient introduction. Thus, only phosphate has a strong, significant correlation with salinity ($r = -0.79$), suggesting the riverine input is the principal source of inorganic phosphorus in the Romanian Black Sea. One possible source of nitrite in coastal environments is

anthropogenic pollution, particularly from sources such as agricultural runoff, industrial discharge, and sewage effluents [97]. These sources can introduce nitrogen compounds, including nitrite, into coastal waters through various pathways, such as surface runoff and groundwater discharge. Additionally, biological processes such as nitrification and denitrification in sediments and water columns [98,99] can also contribute to nitrite levels. Further investigation and monitoring are necessary to identify the specific sources and mechanisms driving nitrite concentrations in coastal waters accurately.

Figure 17. Dissolved inorganic phosphorus interpolated concentrations and chlorophyll *a* means—Romanian Black Sea—2020–2022.

Figure 18. Dissolved inorganic nitrogen interpolated concentrations and chlorophyll *a* means—Romanian Black Sea—2020–2022.

Figure 19. Scatterplots of dissolved inorganic nitrogen (DIN), dissolved inorganic phosphorus (DIP) and chlorophyll *a* concentrations in the Romanian Black Sea waters, 2020–2022 (the red ellipse represents the normal distribution, the dashed red lines represent the prediction interval around the regression line with a confidence of 95%).

Surface nutrient concentrations exhibit strong correlations among themselves, as well as with chlorophyll *a* water column average levels (Figure 20), indicating that areas with higher concentrations of nutrients tend to have higher concentrations of chlorophyll *a*, highlighting the role of nutrients in fuelling phytoplankton blooms. The correlation with salinity is considered as information regarding the potential pathway of nutrient introduction. Thus, only phosphate has a strong, significant correlation with salinity ($r = -0.79$) suggesting the riverine input is the principal source of inorganic phosphorus in the Romanian Black Sea. In this context, the Danube's hydrological patterns, which are affected by climate change [84], could play a part in the phosphorus peaks observed in the transitional waters. In the coastal waters, only nitrite showed a significant correlation with salinity ($r = -0.49$).

One possible source of nitrite in coastal environments is anthropogenic pollution, particularly from sources such as agricultural runoff, industrial discharge, and sewage effluents [97]. These sources introduce nitrogen compounds, including nitrite, into coastal waters through various pathways, such as surface runoff and groundwater discharge. Additionally, biological processes such as nitrification and denitrification in sediments and water columns [98,99] can also contribute to nitrite levels. Further investigation and monitoring are necessary to identify the specific sources and mechanisms driving nitrite concentrations in coastal waters accurately. Currently, only 12% of sewage in Romania is treated in accordance with EU regulations, significantly below the EU average of 76% [100].

The latest River Basin Management Plans (RBMPs) indicate that urban wastewaters contribute significantly to less than “good” water quality in 75% of coastal water bodies while discharges of wastewater from unconnected dwellings contribute significantly to less than “good” water quality in 100% of coastal water bodies. Furthermore, four out of five wastewater treatment plants directly discharging into the Romanian Black Sea fail to meet overall performance standards due to non-compliance with sewage collection and treatment requirements (Figure 1). Despite designating its entire territory as sensitive areas—which requires agglomerations of over 10,000 population equivalents (p.e.) discharging into such areas to implement biological treatment with nitrogen and phosphorus removal—Romania invests only EUR 11 per citizen annually in new collection and treatment infrastructure, well below the EU average of EUR 41 per citizen. Since 2018, the European Union has initiated an infringement case against Romania for failing to meet the standards set by the EU’s Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (Council Directive 91/271/EEC) in its larger urban areas. According to the latest information from Romanian authorities, 189 large agglomerations remain non-compliant with urban wastewater collection requirements, while 198 do not meet treatment standards [101]. Moreover, in 2020, while some large agglomerations still failed to ensure adequate collection of urban wastewater, others were found non-compliant with secondary and the strictest treatment standards, with 188, 192, and 193 large agglomerations, respectively, still falling short [101]. Monitoring data from 2022 show that over 180 large agglomerations in Romania continue to violate both collection and treatment obligations so the infringement case remains active [102].

The challenge posed by small, rural areas experiencing seasonal population surges—similar to those in the Danube Delta and the Romanian southern coast—was effectively addressed in Poland at the Rowy treatment plant. Originally designed to manage urban wastewater for 5000 population equivalent (p.e.) during winter, its capacity triples during the summer months to accommodate increased tourist activity. The plant discharges directly into the Łupawy river. To handle the seasonal flux, the facility underwent significant upgrades to bolster its capacity and integrate more advanced technologies. It now operates in two modes: a reduced capacity ‘winter’ mode for lower volumes of wastewater, and a full capacity ‘summer’ mode for peak periods. These enhancements, which cost around EUR 7.5 million, have also led to energy savings during the winter months [103].

Another significant challenge is adapting stormwater management systems to accommodate climate change impacts. In response, Sweden has developed an innovative approach for wastewater treatment plants discharging into the coastal waters of Malmö. This involves a comprehensive open stormwater system designed to manage a 15-year rainfall event. The system spans 6 km of canals and water channels, incorporates 10 retention ponds, includes 30 green roofs, and features a botanical roof garden atop an old industrial building. Rainwater is initially collected in natural ditches and reservoirs, which then direct the water to a conventional sewer system. This infrastructure is integrated within green spaces that are designed to be temporarily flooded, thus controlling the flow of water into the stormwater system and reducing energy consumption by minimising stormwater runoff into sewage treatment facilities [103].

When comparing to the nutrient concentrations observed in coastal waters, offshore waters demonstrate significantly lower nutrient levels, as evidenced by the lower averages and percentiles across all parameters and the analysis of variance (ANOVA—F test and Kruskal–Wallis test) (Figure 20). Offshore waters exhibit considerably lower concentrations of phosphorus, nitrate, nitrite, ammonium, and dissolved inorganic nitrogen (DIN), indicating an oligotrophic nutrient balance due to the lesser influence of direct runoff and pollution sources found in coastal areas.

In offshore waters, nitrite and phosphate concentrations remain low within the euphotic zone, rise to a peak near the upper boundary of the suboxic zone, and then diminish at the interface of the suboxic and sulphide zone [104–106] (Figure 4). Consequently, a vertical influx of nutrients from the halocline likely serves as the primary nitrogen source in the open sea. This influx sustains phytoplankton within the euphotic layer and facilitates

‘new production’. The dual role of deep waters as both a nutrient sink and source is crucial for maintaining the balance of marine ecosystems, particularly in offshore areas [87]. It plays a pivotal role in biogeochemical cycling, impacting not only local but also global marine ecosystems by influencing primary productivity and carbon cycling [87,107–109]. The nutrient enrichment of surface waters during upwelling supports diverse marine life and can affect fisheries and carbon sequestration processes, which are vital for ecological and economic reasons [110,111].

Figure 20. Spatial variability of nutrients in the Romanian Black Sea grouped by marine reporting units (MRU)—2020–2022.

The nutrient input is the main driver of phytoplankton proliferation, with the highest concentrations of chlorophyll *a* observed in transitional and coastal waters, particularly near the Danube mouths and densely populated areas such as Constanta and Mangalia. Remarkably high values of both nutrients and chlorophyll *a* were also recorded in heavily frequented tourist areas during summer, such as Costinesti and Vama Veche.

Coastal waters also witness the harmful proliferation of *Noctiluca scintillans*, a type of dinoflagellate that blooms under nutrient-rich conditions. These blooms are not just prolific; they are also potentially harmful, capable of producing biotoxins that impact marine life and human health [31,112–114].

With the rise of chlorophyll *a*, the transparency of the water exponentially decreases. The data reveal a gradient of increasing seawater’s transparency as moving away from the coast to offshore waters (where the maximum was 21 m), reflecting a decrease in nutrient concentrations and eutrophication impacts, and highlighting the need for effective nutrient

management practices in coastal zones to restore and maintain water clarity and overall marine health in the Black Sea.

The reduction in transparency is significant because it affects the ability of sunlight to penetrate the water column, which can disrupt the photosynthetic activities of deeper-dwelling aquatic plants and affect the visual predators in the ecosystem [115,116]. The heavy tourist areas, particularly those along the coast like Costinesti and Vama Veche, witness especially decreases in water transparency, impacting both the ecological and recreational values of the coastal waters. Moreover, opportunistic macroalgae, such as *Ulva* spp., *Cladophora* spp., and *Ceramium* spp., thrive in such environments with reduced water transparency. When water transparency decreases, it affects the light availability deeper in the water column, which can inhibit the growth of other, light-dependent marine plants and phytoplankton. Opportunistic macroalgae, however, are often capable of surviving and even prospering in lower light conditions compared to their competitors [117]. They can effectively utilise the available light more efficiently or have mechanisms that allow them to capture light across a broader spectrum. The same nutrient enrichment (eutrophication) that causes increased algal blooms and reduces water transparency also benefits opportunistic macroalgae [118]. These algae are typically highly efficient at uptaking and using available nutrients, such as nitrogen and phosphorus, which are abundant in eutrophic waters. Their rapid growth rates allow them to quickly exploit these conditions before other species can establish themselves. Opportunistic macroalgae typically have fast growth rates and can reproduce both sexually and asexually, allowing them to quickly colonise and dominate available spaces. This rapid proliferation can occur especially when their competitors are weakened by reduced light penetration or other stressors associated with turbid waters. Opportunistic macroalgae also proliferated in significant amounts (Figures 21 and 22). While the presence of opportunistic species suggests a relatively healthy nutrient-rich environment, the overall ecological status assessment based on the EI indicator indicates unfavorable conditions. Meanwhile, significant quantities of macroalgae reach the shore every year (Photo 1 and Photo 2). According to data from the Romanian Water Authority (<https://www.rmri.ro/Home/InfoWarnings.Info.html#> accessed on 25 April 2024), between 2020 and 2022, significant quantities of macroalgae were collected from the Romanian coast, amounting to 8080 t, 16,758 t, and 12,650 t, respectively, each year.

However, no phenomena of anoxia or hypoxia were recorded in 2020–2022, although in some summer periods water stratification and temperature increase lead to a decrease in saturation in the deep layers, helping to maintain a predominantly good condition of macrozoobenthos.

The data demonstrate a clear and urgent need for enhanced nutrient management strategies in the coastal zone to combat eutrophication and achieve environmental standards. Measures might include improved wastewater treatment, stricter agricultural runoff controls, and targeted remediation projects. Moreover, continuous monitoring and adaptive management are essential to address this complex issue effectively, aiming to reduce nutrient inputs and restore the ecological balance of these waters.

Although, in some areas, exceedances are relatively small, they highlight the importance of ongoing monitoring and management efforts to address nutrient inputs and maintain the overall health and integrity of marine ecosystems. Continued caution and targeted interventions will be essential to ensure the long-term sustainability of marine environments in the face of evolving environmental challenges.

Lately, there has been a slight reduction in the eutrophication pressure on the Black Sea ecosystem. Initial indications of improvement are visible in the pelagic communities, yet the response of zoobenthic communities is slower, with signs of recovery remaining uncertain [119]. Nonetheless, within the community of marine ecologists, there is an increasing acknowledgement that the physical and biological characteristics of marine ecosystems can function as a filter, potentially altering responses to shifts in nutrient inputs, frequently in a nonlinear way [3,88,120–123]. BEAST, by integrating several criteria that characterise eutrophication in its different moments—from the introduction of nutrients to

the proliferation of phytoplankton, harmful blooms and the reduction of transparency and oxygen content of bottom waters, captures the phenomenon and offers a complete picture to policymakers and all stakeholders.

Figure 21. Macroalgae deposits on the Southern littoral—Romanian Black Sea—9 July 2020 (source: <https://ziare.com/stiri/eveniment/video-tone-de-alge-pe-litoral-specialistii-nu-au-solutii-pentru-a-rezolva-problema-1618850> accessed on 25 April 2024).

Figure 22. Macroalgae deposits on the Southern littoral—Romanian Black Sea—11 July 2022 (source: <https://www.antena3.ro/actualitate/locale/marea-verde-marea-neagra-sute-tone-de-alge-sud-litoral-645564.html> accessed on 25 April 2024).

Eutrophication, particularly through Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs), has numerous societal impacts, leading to significant economic investments in both the EU and the

Black Sea sub-region to mitigate threats to local economies, living resources, and public health [25]. The most critical human health threat comes from HAB toxin production, which incurs high costs due to necessary monitoring programs for toxins in shellfish, fish, and drinking water to reduce public exposure [124]. Acute illnesses and mortality from these toxins are well-documented, while the long-term effects of chronic exposure to low toxin levels are less understood and increasingly researched [125].

Beyond direct health concerns, public perception of coastal health, which affects consumer safety and confidence among coastal inhabitants, is influenced by water colour, clarity, and odour; the abundance of fish and shellfish; and governmental advisories regarding unseen microbes and toxins [14].

Quantifying the cost of eutrophication as an environmental issue is challenging because there is no absolute definition of when nutrient enrichment becomes problematic, i.e., when it leads to adverse effects [14]. Algal and higher plant growth depend on a combination of interdependent hydrochemical, geographic, and climatic factors. Consequently, a specific nutrient level might cause adverse effects and associated costs in one water body but not in another, or in the same water body at a different time. Additionally, the threshold at which nutrient enrichment becomes problematic varies. The core issue lies in understanding the relationships between nutrient enrichment, its effects, and the resulting costs [14].

The feasibility of effectively managing eutrophication in the Romanian Black Sea region should address several key factors. The socio-economic factors regarding implementing sustainable agricultural practices and upgrading wastewater treatment facilities are economically demanding [14]. However, financial incentives, subsidies, and long-term economic benefits, such as improved fisheries and tourism, can make these measures feasible [126]. Tailored financial support is essential for smaller farmers and communities with limited resources. Moreover, effective stakeholder engagement is feasible through enhancing inclusive decision-making processes, public awareness campaigns, and educational initiatives. While challenging, fostering collaboration among diverse groups, such as local communities, industries, and governments, can be achieved through structured platforms for dialogue and participation [126].

Developing and enforcing stricter regulations on nutrient inputs is feasible with strong political will and robust institutional frameworks. Financial incentives for compliance and penalties for non-compliance can drive adherence to regulations. Integrated Coastal Zone Management (ICZM) can streamline efforts and mitigate conflicting uses [127].

Regarding technological innovations, the adoption of precision farming, advanced wastewater treatment technologies, and real-time monitoring systems is feasible but requires substantial initial investment and technical training. Innovations in these areas are rapidly advancing, making their implementation more accessible over time [128].

About the international cooperation, given the geopolitical complexity of the Black Sea, international cooperation is challenging but feasible through sub-regional agreements and collaborative projects since the Black Sea Commission is weakened by the war in Ukraine. Engagement from both EU and non-EU countries, supported by international organisations (e.g., ICPDR—International Commission for the Protection of the Danube River), can facilitate coordinated actions and resource sharing.

The challenges of the overall feasibility are high initial costs, coordination among diverse stakeholders, enforcement of regulations, and technological limitations in some areas. But the opportunities, like the long-term benefits of improved water quality, ecosystem health, and economic opportunities, provide strong incentives. Advancements in technology and international support can enhance the feasibility of managing eutrophication effectively [129]. Thus, while there are considerable challenges to implementing measures to manage eutrophication in the Romanian Black Sea, the combination of targeted interventions, stakeholder engagement, robust policies, and technological innovations makes it a feasible goal with long-term environmental and economic benefits.

The spatial variability of eutrophication in the Black Sea shows distinct differences between coastal and offshore waters, driven by various factors related to nutrient inputs and environmental conditions. Transitional and coastal waters exhibit significantly higher nutrient levels, particularly inorganic nitrogen and phosphorus, primarily due to the Danube's input, agricultural runoff, urbanisation, industrial discharge, and insufficiently treated wastewater. These nutrient enrichments lead to frequent and intense algal blooms, including harmful algal blooms like *Noctiluca scintillans*, and reduced water transparency, which adversely affects marine life. In contrast, offshore waters have lower nutrient concentrations, influenced by dilution, lesser direct runoff, and natural processes such as upwelling and vertical mixing. While offshore waters also experience phytoplankton blooms, they are less frequent and intense compared to coastal areas. The proximity to direct nutrient sources, hydrological influence from the Danube River, and human activities significantly impact coastal waters, whereas offshore waters are more affected by oceanographic processes.

Our study indicates that achieving good environmental status (GES) regarding eutrophication in the transitional waters, representing the marine part of the Danube Delta Biosphere Reserve, could be possible if concentrations of inorganic phosphorus (DIP) and inorganic nitrogen (DIN) are reduced by 55% and 43%, respectively. In coastal waters, which are heavily influenced by urbanisation, industry, and seasonal tourism, reductions of 38% in DIP and 37% in DIN are necessary. These ambitious targets require significant efforts and the establishment in future research of a total daily maximum load for nutrients per activity.

Several potential challenges and limitations for assessing eutrophication in the Romanian Black Sea resulted from this study. Thus, the variability in data availability, both spatially and temporally, can skew the representation of eutrophication dynamics and the assessments made using the Black Sea Eutrophication Assessment Tool (BEAST). On the other hand, while the BEAST is robust, it has inherent limitations that might overlook certain ecological or chemical processes, and distinguishing between human-induced changes and natural variability in nutrient levels and eutrophication impacts can be challenging. Moreover, the current understanding of climate impacts on eutrophication might not fully account for rapid climatic changes that could alter ecosystem responses. Future research needs to better integrate the effects of climate change on eutrophication dynamics.

5. Conclusions

The analysis of eutrophication in the Romanian Black Sea presents a complex situation, with low levels in offshore waters but significant challenges in transitional, coastal, and shelf areas. In transitional waters, particularly within the Danube Delta Biosphere Reserve, a reduction of 55% in inorganic phosphorus and 43% in inorganic nitrogen concentrations is necessary to achieve good environmental status. Coastal waters, impacted by urbanisation, industry, and tourism, require reductions of 38% and 37% in these nutrients, respectively.

Effective management of eutrophication demands targeted interventions and stricter regulations on nutrient inputs from sources like agricultural runoff, industrial discharges, and wastewater treatment. Implementing sustainable agricultural practices such as precision farming, cover cropping, and the establishment of buffer zones alongside waterways is critical. Urban and rural planning must also prioritise infrastructure improvements to reduce pollution, particularly in coastal zones.

Additionally, integrated coastal zone management that combines land-based and marine strategies, zoning regulations, and ecosystem-based approaches is essential to mitigate conflicting uses and reduce eutrophication impacts. Public awareness and stakeholder engagement are also crucial in fostering collaborative approaches to nutrient pollution management.

Given the Black Sea's geographical and political complexity, involving multiple countries, international cooperation extends beyond EU borders, making it essential for effectively managing eutrophication. The study also suggests a need for ongoing research to

address gaps in the data and enhance modelling approaches to better understand and predict eutrophication dynamics, including the impacts of climate change.

Ultimately, the combination of local actions, regional coordination, and international collaboration will be key to managing and mitigating eutrophication in the Romanian Black Sea effectively.

Supplementary Materials: The following supporting information can be downloaded at: <https://www.mdpi.com/article/10.3390/su16125146/s1>, Table S1. Methodology for sampling protocols and analytical techniques, Table S2. Methods used for D5 elements analysis and evaluation, Table S3. Overview of criteria, indicators, and thresholds (based on Commission Decision 848/2017—Descriptor 5).

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